

International Journal of Innovations in Liberal Arts

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10999572>

A Comparative Study in the Public and Private Education Sector

Pooja, Neha Yadav, and Shubham Saini

Amity School of Liberal Arts
Amity University Haryana, India

Received: DEC. 23, 2023

Accepted: JAN. 28, 2024

Published: FEB. 28, 2024

ABSTRACT

A comparison of private and public institutions is made with regards to their gross enrollment ratio, steps taken to increase enrollment, quality, co-curricular activities, and evaluation system. Private schools focus on quality of education. Education goes beyond merely teaching the learning process and also includes other activities that affect outcomes. The learning outcomes become relevant or enjoyable when students are actively engaged in their learning program. There is a steady growth in private schools/universities, and there is a decline in public schools/universities. Data shows that the private sector is the fastest growing sector in higher education. The reputation of private schools/universities in India has gained national and international recognition.

Keywords: Private schools, public schools, Growth, Quality Education, Learning Outcomes, Enrollment.

Introduction

In order for a country to develop, education is extremely important. We achieve economic and social prosperity through education, which is the foundation for development. Increasing economic efficiency and social cohesion requires this strategy. By enhancing the value and efficiency of their work, helps poor people escape poverty.

Basic education is the first subject Essential to the life of every country and every individual Man. These are the first stairs that successfully reach a nation's desired goal by crossing it successfully. It is said that the closer the relationship is with the national life, the primary education is not the same as the secondary and the higher education. The national ideology of primary education and the contribution of the character are greatly contributed.

Primary education is not related to any particular class or person but to the entire population. It has every contact with every person's life at every step (Shrivastava, 2007). In addition to offering children secure places in

which to develop, elementary schools also give them the drive and know-how necessary to deal with a variety of situations. Additionally, attending school puts kids in a better position to learn new concepts and have the opportunity to spend more time with peers who support the growth of their personalities and unique skill sets.

Additionally, kids who thrive in elementary school develop into socially adept and sound emotional states. They grow excited to take up new projects and challenges with the vigor and determination that kids are known to own. Consequently, these kids grow up to be more diligent in their academic endeavors, and they maintain their academic advancement evolution. They don't just progress in academics, but also in terms of their social skills, as they show empathy for others, and they establish sincere friendships with their mates. (Harman & Jones, 2003).

According to education ministry data in FY22, school enrolment stood at 26.5 crore children with 19.4 lakh additional children enrolled in Primary to Higher Secondary levels. Total conscription of Children with Special Needs (CWSN) in FY22 stands at 22.7 lakh as compared to 21.9 lakh in FY21, which is an increase of 3.3 percent. The enrolments increased across all levels viz., Primary, Upper-Primary, Secondary, and Higher Secondary except for the Pre-Primary level. At the Preprimary level, enrolment reduced from 1.1 crore in FY21 to 1.0 crore in FY22. During the year, about 1.0 crore children were enrolled in pre-primary, 12.2 crore in Primary, 6.7 crore in Upper Primary, 3.9 crore in Secondary, and 2.9 crore in Higher Secondary.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the gross enrollment ratio of government and private schools at the elementary level.
2. To compare the co-curricular activities organized by the government and private schools at the elementary level.
3. To compare the strategies adopted by teachers in government and private schools to increase student enrollment.
4. To compare the evaluation system adopted by teachers of government schools and teachers of private schools at the elementary level.

Research Question

1. What factors influence the gross enrollment ratio in both types of schools?
2. What types of co-curricular activities are commonly offered by government and private schools at the elementary level?
3. What are the common strategies used by teachers in government and private schools to increase student enrollment?
4. What are the common methods of evaluation used by teachers in government and private schools at the elementary level?

Significance of the Study

The most important time in a child's life is during their elementary school years. A child's primary school education is the cornerstone of his life, during which he constructs the magnificent structure. The child's complete development is dependent on this education. The results of scientific investigations on the state of primary education often contribute to the effectiveness and efficiency of that education. This study is important from many points of view. A few studies have been conducted on different aspects of elementary education in different areas, but no study was conducted related to the present topic. This study is also important as to studies the gross enrollment ratio, steps taken to increase the enrollment, quality, co-curricular activities, and evaluation system in both the education sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Kingdom G. (1997), "The Quality and Efficiency of Private and Public education: A case study of Urban India". Government and Private schools are similar in their cost-efficiency but compare unfavorably with Private schools. The quality and cost-efficiency of government-founded schools need to be greatly improved and private schools would lead to a gain in efficiency as these institutions are both merely technically efficient and more cost-efficient. Bedi et al. (2000) conducted a study on "The effectiveness of public versus private schools." The result of the study revealed that the performance of private schools was better than public schools. Verma (2017) compared the attitude of parents for opting to educate their children in private schools rather than in public schools. The investigator found that the private school provides better infrastructure facilities, better education, and a better teaching environment and also had the good and dedicated teachers than public schools. Ranjan (2014), "Private universities in India & quality of education": He said that private higher education in India is getting more competitive with a remarkable increase in the number of academic institutions in the country. Only a few private schools/ universities in India have gained both national and international reputations and quality achieved at the desired level for developing skills but all of them are functioning with the same level of efficiency. Tiwari (2013), ANJUM (2013), Khurana (2013), "Role of private sector in Indian higher education". The exponential growth in private higher education institutes needs to be regulated based on the quality of outcomes. because government higher education needs to improve. The central government funding on education is less than 1% of GDP. At the current budgetary allocation for education, the funds would be insufficient private sector can bridge the gap between budgetary allocation and required allocation.

METHODOLOGY

In the present study, the descriptive survey method was used by the investigator. It is a scientific method that involves describing and analyzing the collected data in a numerical form. As for sample and sampling technique, the entire government and private schools at the elementary level of Gurugram district in Haryana constituted the sample of the present study. All the students and teachers of government and private schools at the elementary level were considered. Two blocks of Gurugram district were selected as sample of the study through a random sampling technique. In the second stage 5 government and 5 private schools at the elementary level were selected from these two blocks through a random sampling technique. As for data collection, a self-developed questionnaire was administered to students at a school in Gurugram district. Primary data: A visit to 5 different private schools and 5 government school were made, where a student was asked about the teaching activities, co-curricular activities, teacher interaction, and personal counseling by a teacher, and teachers were also questioned about student performance, student involvement, and different evaluation system adopted by them as dealt in the questionnaire. Secondary data: The student enrollment ratio at the elementary level at the private and public schools has been taken from the government site and school administration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The analysis revealed that the gross enrollment ratio is better in private schools than the government schools. The Gross Enrollment ratio of males is higher in private schools than in government schools whereas the female student ratio in government schools is more than the private schools.
2. It showed that 100% of government and private schools organized daily morning assemblies, sports programs, and cleanliness programs in the schools
3. It indicated the Steps taken by the selected Government and private schools to increase the enrollment of students. Item No. 1 of the table shows that 100% of Government schools spread awareness among the parents regarding different government schemes and facilities provided by the government while 20% of Private schools spread awareness among the parents regarding different government schemes and facilities provided by the government for the students and 80% did not do the same
4. It revealed the evaluation system adopted by the government and private schools for the assessment of the students at elementary level. It was observed that 60% government schools evaluated the students after completion of every lesson, 40% government schools never evaluated the students after completion of every lesson. On the other hand, 100% Private schools always evaluated the students after

completion of every lesson. 80% government schools evaluated students after completion of every unit and 20% government schools never evaluated the students after completion of every unit. On the other hand, 100% Private schools always evaluated the students after completion of every unit. 100% government schools as well as private schools evaluated the students at the end of every month at elementary level.

5. It was found that the majority of government and private schools at the elementary level took various steps to increase student enrollment
6. It was found that co-curricular activities are organized by both government and private schools at the elementary level to a good and satisfactory extent.
7. It was found that 60% of government schools evaluate the students after completion of every lesson, 80% evaluate the students after completion of every unit and 100% evaluate the students at the end of every month. On the other hand, 100% of private schools at the elementary level evaluate the students after completion of every lesson, every unit, and also at the end of every month.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the results of the study, it may be concluded that government and private schools have a lot of differences in many aspects including gender gross enrollment, the strategies adopted for increasing the enrollment ratio of students, different evaluation systems, etc. Findings revealed that private schools have better gender enrollment ratios better teaching and learning environments, and better evaluation systems, while 100% of government schools spread awareness among the students regarding government schemes and facilities. So, to make the government schools at the elementary level better, some steps should be taken, such as:

1. Making the administrative system stronger
2. Proving teacher training
3. Making teachers aware of the scientific method of teaching
4. Adopting a proper evaluation system
5. Arrangement of lab and canteen facilities
6. Making a strong bond among the stakeholders etc.

As we know elementary-level education is the base of higher education, so it is a very significant level of education. Because to develop more human resources it is important to make the foundation level stronger i.e., the elementary level. The more production of human resources will lead to more economic growth of the whole nation. Therefore elementary-level education is very important from an economic point of view also. Hence both government and private schools at the elementary level need to be stronger and sufficient according to students' needs to make them prepare for higher education.

References

<https://educationforallindia.com/private-vs-public-education-impact-on-studentoutcomes/#:~:text=While%20public%20schools%20are%20typically,able%20to%20afford%20private%20education.>

https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/programmes/7thSurvey%20Reports/Enrolment_in_school.pdf

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343402731_Comparative_study_of_the_quality_of_Education_in_public_and_private_schools

<https://img.asercentre.org/docs/ASER%202021/ASER%202020%20wave%201%20-%20v2/state%20estimates/haryana.pdf>

<https://www.questionpro.com/blog/student-survey/>

<https://www.template.net/blog/school/improving-quality-education/>